

**METHODOLOGICAL FEATURES OF THE ORGANIZATION OF
WORK ON THE USE OF INTERNET RESOURCES FOR
EDUCATIONAL PURPOSES**

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ABSTRACT: The article deals with methodological features of the organization of work on the use of Internet resources for educational purposes, components, processes and stages of them. Basic principles and reflections of such methods in language teaching have fully been stated. Main methodological and theoretical approaches of these features have been clearly analyzed.

KEYWORDS: multimedia teaching tools, lack of a language barrier, effective assistance, activating, personality-oriented, intercultural communication,

In modern society, the role of foreign languages is increasingly increasing. Knowledge of a foreign language gives young people the opportunity to join the world culture, use the potential of the vast resources of the global Internet in their activities, as well as work with information and communication technologies and multimedia teaching tools.

The purpose of teaching a foreign language is the communicative activity of students, that is, practical knowledge of a foreign language. The tasks of the teacher are to activate the activity of each student in the learning process, to create situations for their creative activity. The main purpose of teaching a foreign language to students is to educate a person who is willing and able to communicate, people who are willing and able to receive self-education. Participation in various international programs, the opportunity to study abroad presuppose not only a high level of foreign language proficiency, but also certain personality traits: sociability, lack of a language barrier, knowledge of international etiquette, a broad outlook, the ability

to “present” yourself. As a rule, when performing various tests when entering a higher educational institution or participating in competitions and Olympiads, which requires a special type of training. To achieve all these goals, of course, the use of computer technologies and Internet resources in teaching English and presentations provides effective assistance to the teacher.

The computer, nowadays, is a very important and independent thing. Many children and even adults use it only to play computer games. But, fortunately, there are many who have found the right use for it. For example, he helps with his studies. It is very convenient when there is such an assistant at hand, because we can print abstracts, reports, in a word, everything we need without leaving home. In addition, a computer can help in learning a foreign language. After all, there are a lot of CDs, electronic textbooks, multimedia training programs that lead to good results in learning English.

Therefore, the purpose of this work: the theoretical foundations of the use of computer technology in the process of teaching a foreign language. To achieve this goal, it is necessary to solve the following tasks: consideration of the theoretical foundations of the use of computer technologies in the process of teaching a foreign language; analysis of methodological features of the organization of work on the use of Internet resources for educational purposes; a study of the practical use of a computer in foreign language lessons.

The latest ICTs are taking more and more place in our lives. Their use in foreign language lessons increases the motivation and cognitive activity of students, expands their horizons and allows them to apply the personality-oriented technology of interactive learning, i.e. learning in interaction.

The use of information and communication technologies in the educational process helps to intensify and individualize learning, increases interest in the subject, and makes it possible to avoid subjective evaluation. The use of computers and digital educational resources in teaching English helps students overcome the

psychological barrier to using a foreign language as a means of communication.

The use of modern information and computer technologies in the activities of a foreign language teacher as a means of activating the creative potential of students.

The desire to learn the language of another people is currently an urgent necessity dictated by changes in the life of society.

A foreign language has firmly entered our lives, demonstrating its attractiveness and great potential opportunities for the development of the personality of students. But in order to form a stable positive motivation of students in relation to a foreign language, in order to achieve the most optimal assimilation of its basic level at school, it is necessary to find the most accessible, promising and interesting teaching methods and techniques for students that would allow everyone to show their activity, creativity, and raise the bar of personal self-esteem.

Information technologies and computer-based learning tools provide unique opportunities to improve the effectiveness of a foreign language teacher.

Using them in foreign language lessons increases the motivation and cognitive activity of students, expands their horizons and allows them to apply a personality-oriented technology of interactive foreign language teaching, i.e. learning in interaction.

Information technologies play an important role in teaching foreign languages. But there are contradictions and difficulties in this issue, which are quite common:

between the increasing growth of the information flow and the real willingness of students to carry out foreign language communication, seeking mutual understanding with native speakers of a foreign language;

between the needs of students in their creative self-realization in educational and cognitive activities and the lack of development of individual educational trajectories of students in a traditional school;

between the optimal satisfaction of individual information needs of the individual and the objective need for humanization and humanization of society as a whole, which brings the system of language education to a new stage, the product of which is a person who is able to competently and effectively engage in intercultural communication based on the dialogue of cultures [13, p.146].

The use of computer technology allows the student to overcome the psychological barrier to using a foreign language as a means of communication. One of the manifestations of this barrier is the so-called "fear of error". Students note that when using computer technology, they do not feel awkward making mistakes, and receive fairly clear instructions on how to overcome the mistake.

Therefore, the task of the teacher is to identify ways to improve the effectiveness of teaching English through the introduction of information technologies into the educational process, which allow students to activate their creative potential and form their communicative competence.

In modern pedagogical practice, various teaching technologies are used, with the help of which students' interest in the subject sharply increases, academic performance increases, and the level of intellectual culture increases.

The use of computer and information technologies at the second and third stages of education allows students to better prepare for the final certification in English in accordance with the requirements of the state standard. In the learning process, students not only improve the knowledge they acquired during the previous period of study, but also expand their vocabulary, taking into account practical knowledge of a foreign language in standard situations (within the framework of studied monologue statements with elements of reasoning and dialogical conversations in the form of an exchange of opinions).

In the process of using information technology by a teacher, students realize creative activities, which includes the ability to ask, explain, study, describe, compare, analyze, evaluate, express their opinions and judgments, argue them,

conduct an independent search for necessary information, navigate the text in English, make brief messages on a given topic.

All of the above will allow students to use the acquired knowledge and skills in practice and everyday life to communicate with representatives of other countries; to obtain information from foreign-language sources of information necessary for educational purposes; to expand opportunities in choosing future professional activities; to study the values of world culture, cultural heritage and achievements of other countries; to familiarize representatives of foreign countries with culture and the achievements of Uzbekistan.

Animated slides are used in the process of forming lexical and grammatical skills. To show, highlight which elements or objects should be paid attention to so that the necessary information appears at a certain time. You can superimpose sound, for example, for conducting lexical dictation, relaxation, or for other purposes.

When improving skills, a testing document is used, which can be created in Microsoft Word using hyperlinks. It looks more colorful in PowerPoint. The test result is immediately visible on the demo screen, which always delights students if their answers match the correct answers on the screen. A presentation on the topic of the lesson in the process of activating new material allows the teacher not to make notes on the blackboard, which means there is more time to consolidate. The third stage is the development of skills in working with multimedia software by students, which proves the success of work to activate their creative potential.

Computers have rapidly entered our lives and into the process of teaching English, somewhat displacing traditional methods and forcing foreign language teachers to solve problems that no linguist even suspected existed a few years ago.

In the technology of computer training programs, the ideas of cognitive linguistics, methodology and psychology are embodied in the dynamics of

development. Information training programs allow you to model certain linguistic tasks, for example, the ability to cope with difficult fragments of a readable text, the formation and consolidation of grammatical skills, the ability to conduct a dialogue in typical situations. At the same time, the system monitors the student's actions and corrects his mistakes. Computerization of the pedagogical knowledge control procedure allows for a more comprehensive and objective verification of the student's level of knowledge [14, p.76].

Borrowing and applying the existing experience in the field of information technology in the context of teaching a foreign language, I am developing new options for their use in teaching English, allowing to optimize the content of the educational process and increase the efficiency of learning educational material.

The use of information technology elements in lessons contributes to the formation of students' skills to work with various information, a critical attitude to it, develops logical thinking, provides information and emotional saturation of lessons, increases students' interest in the subject, activates their creative potential, and also ensures the connection of educational material with the surrounding life [4, p.15].

Currently, various forms of organization of the educational process are used. Since information technology is both a means of presenting material and a controlling means, such technologies ensure high quality of presentation of material and use various communication channels (text, sound, graphic, touch, etc.). All this allows to increase the motivation of students and form their communicative competence.

Forms of work with computer programs include the study of vocabulary, practicing pronunciation, teaching dialogic and monological speech, teaching writing, practicing grammatical phenomena. This determines the nature of the exercises and methodological techniques used. The most commonly used are the following:

A question-and-answer dialogue. The essence of the student's work is to give direct answers to computer questions, using the language material contained in the question as a basis and scheme.

A dialog with a selective response. To answer the computer, the student chooses one of a number of suggested options.

A dialogue with a freely constructed answer. Such a dialogue is provided by the program with all possible answers to each question posed by the computer, so that the latter can "find out" and evaluate the correctness of the answer.

Exercises to fill in the gaps. The computer offers the student a text or a set of sentences with omissions. It is necessary to fill in the gaps using a hint in the form of Uzbek words that need to be translated into a foreign language and used in the right form. You can also fill in the gaps with words or phrases, choosing them from the computer's suggestions.

The methodical purpose of any lesson in the learning system is to create conditions for the manifestation of cognitive activity of students and the development of their intellectual abilities. This is achieved in the following ways:

A computer as a simulator in the process of forming skills. For this purpose, the lessons use:

The Microsoft Word program is for exercises on the correctness of writing the studied words, constructing sentences, transforming sentences, issuing theory and performing training exercises.

Microsoft PowerPoint program - using the tools of this program, you can create good simulators for introducing new vocabulary and grammar. For example: presentation (vocabulary and/or grammar) + a series of exercises (with right-wrong control) + voicing + a control test or exercise.

Microsoft Excel program - using this program, you can also create similar exercises with summarizing the results of testing, the number of mistakes made, and returning to incorrectly executed sentences. Computer - as a visual aid for the

organization of active educational and cognitive activities:

The Microsoft Power Point program. With the help of this program, in English lessons on the subject, you can present materials of a regional nature, introduce new vocabulary, grammatical rules, create materials for listening, etc.

The Microsoft Excel program is used to demonstrate charts, graphs, and pivot tables.

The use of information technology in the classroom provides a lasting result, primarily through the use of the creative potential of students, which leads to the formation of a situation of success and increases motivation in learning.

The pedagogical process is cooperation with the student, when the teacher helps in overcoming difficulties, explains, shows, reminds, outlines, sums up, advises, confers, prevents, empathizes, encourages, stimulates, inspires confidence, interests, inspires, gives the student the joy of communication, helps the student to develop, improve.

Thus, information and computer technologies are a means of activating creative potential and improving the quality of knowledge when learning a foreign language [13, p.98].

Information technologies are only for teachers who are looking for and who love to learn new things. They are for those who care about the level of their professional competence, who are concerned about how much he, a teacher of a modern Uzbek school, meets the requirements of the coming century.

Conclusion

The tasks of modernizing education cannot be solved without the optimal implementation of information technology in all its spheres. The use of information technology gives impetus to the development of new forms and content of traditional activities of students, which leads to their implementation at a higher level. Computer work should be organized in such a way that from the very first

lessons of the initial stage of education it becomes a powerful psychological and pedagogical means of forming a need-motivational plan for schoolchildren, a means of maintaining and further developing their interest in the subject being studied. Properly organized work of students with a computer can contribute, in particular, to the growth of their cognitive and communicative interest, which in turn will contribute to the activation and expansion of opportunities for independent work of students to master English, both in the classroom and outside of school hours. An important feature of a computer in the educational process of a foreign language is that it can be an “interlocutor” of the student, i.e. work in a communicative-directed dialog mode and in a certain way, for example, from graphical means, an analyzer and a speech synthesizer to make up for the absence of a natural communicant, modeling and imitating his non-verbal and speech behavior. The computer allows you to present on the display screen elements of a regional nature, features of the environment and the environment, which can be used as a background for the formation of speech activity in a foreign language among students. The computer has great capabilities for constructing color images that can be transformed within the specified limits. The noted capabilities of the computer make it an excellent technical tool for various kinds of explanations and generalizations of the phenomena of language, speech, and speech activity.

REFERENCES

- 1.Afanasyeva O.V., Mikheeva I.V. English: Studies for 6th grade with in-depth study. English - 2nd ed. - Moscow: Prosveshchenie, 1999
2. Ayapova T.A. Program on the subject “Foreign language” // Foreign languages in schools of Kazakhstan. - 2002. - №1
- 3.Belyaeva L.A., Ivanova N.V. PowerPoint presentation and its possibilities in teaching foreign languages //Foreign languages at school.2008, No.4.

4. Bershadsky, M. Information competence./Public education. 2009 - No.4. - p.139
5. Bogorditskaya V.N., Khrustaleva L.V. Studies. Eng. Language: For 8th grade. With a deepening. Studied. English 4th edition - Moscow: 2001
6. Borisova E.M. Project in German lessons // Foreign Languages at school. - 1998. - №2
7. Brown, D.R. Problem solving model for the development of information literacy
8. Karamysheva T.V. Learning foreign languages using a computer (in questions and answers). St. Petersburg, 2001.
9. Karpov A.S. The Internet in the training of future foreign language teachers. IYaSh, No.4, 2002. pp. 73-78.
10. Kisunko E.I., Muzlanova E.S. Interactive teaching of English to students in grades 10-11 using computer technology // English, Publishing house "The first of September". 2007, №16.
11. Sysoev P.V., Evstigneeva M.N. Modern educational Internet resources in teaching a foreign language // Foreign languages at school. 2008, No.6.
12. Telitsina T.N. The use of computer programs in English lessons. IYaSh, No.2. 2002.
13. Ushakova S.V. Computer in English lessons. IYaSh, No.5, 1997 pp. 40-41.
14. Tsvetkova L.A. The use of a computer in teaching vocabulary in elementary school. IYASH, No. 2, 2002. pp. 43-47.
15. World Book 's CD-ROM encyclopaedia, Topics Entertainment.- 2003
16. Xamzayev, A. (2020). The background of teaching grammar through games. Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI, 1(88). извлечено от https://science.iedu.uz/index.php/archive_jspi/article/view/7092
17. Xamzayev, A. (2020). Different Permanent Associations That Express Public Life In English and The Problems Of Translating Them Into Uzbek

Language. Архив Научных Публикаций JSPI, 1(90). извлечено от
https://science.i-edu.uz/index.php/archive_jspi/article/view/6989